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ABSTRACT

Spinal health in children is of critical importance as it forms the basis of lifelong musculoskeletal health. During childhood, the spine undergoes rapid growth, making it vulnerable to postural imbalances and biomechanical stressors such as improper backpack use or sedentary lifestyles. Factors including physical inactivity, prolonged screen time, poor ergonomics, and inadequate nutrition exacerbate risks, potentially leading to chronic pain, functional limitations, and compromised quality of life. Early detection through routine pediatric screenings and school-based programs is vital to identify abnormalities such as spinal curvature or postural disorders before they progress. Treatments range from physical therapy and corrective bracing to surgical options in severe cases. Preventive strategies emphasize promoting physical activity, ergonomic adaptations (e.g., appropriately weighted backpacks, supportive furniture), and postural education to mitigate risks. Prioritizing spinal health in childhood not only safeguards immediate physical development but also reduces the burden of chronic musculoskeletal disorders in adulthood. This article provides an overview of the prevalence of spinal disorders, the influence of lifestyle factors such as physical activity and backpack use, and the importance of education. Recent studies have emphasized the need to raise awareness of the importance of spinal health among parents, educators, and family physicians. Furthermore, this article underlines the need for preventive measures and early interventions to reduce the risk of spinal disorders in children.

KEYWORDS

Scoliosis, education, backpack, spinal health

INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS) has been shown to be between 0.35% and 5.2% in the world and is generally accepted to be 2-3% in children under 16 years of age. In the study conducted by Yılmaz et al., the prevalence of AIS in Turkey was found to be 2.3% (Yılmaz, Zateri, Kusvuran Ozkan, Kayalar, & Berk, 2020). Although these rates show regional differences, they cannot be neglected. Spinal health is an important part of systemic health that significantly affects the physical development and quality of life of children. Recent studies have shown that spinal disorders, including back pain and postural deformities, are becoming increasingly common among children and adolescents (Joergensen et al., 2019; Sainz de Baranda et al., 2020). The increase in the incidence of these disorders can be attributed to several factors, including sedentary lifestyles, improper backpack use, and lack of awareness of spinal health (Patil, Sumana, & Shagale, 2016). Moreover, physiological differences between the spines of children and adults require special approaches for the prevention and treatment of the disease (Ambrosio et al., 2023). The importance of education in spinal health cannot be underestimated. Studies have shown that children, parents, and educators often have limited knowledge about spinal anatomy, pathology, and the consequences of poor spinal health (Lauridsen & Hestbæk, 2013; Louw et al., 2021). This lack of knowledge may lead to neglect of spine care, resulting in long-term adverse effects on children's health. Therefore, it is very important to implement educational programs that promote spine health awareness (Park & Kim, 2011). The aim of this study is to identify, through systematic review, the key factors that influence spinal health in children, common issues to be aware of, and practical steps that parents and caregivers can take to support a strong and healthy spine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A systematic review of recent literature was conducted to investigate the current state of spinal health in children. The review focused on studies published in peer-reviewed journals addressing various aspects of spine health, including epidemiology, risk factors, and educational programs. This study does not require ethics committee approval.

RESULTS

In a PubMed search on ‘spine health in children,’ 1510 articles were identified, 16 of which were evaluated. Articles that mentioned adult spine health in general and emphasized surgical treatment options were excluded from the study. The remaining studies were included in the systematic review and meta-analysis.

DISCUSSION

The findings obtained from the literature review revealed some important information about spinal health in children. Firstly, spinal pain is a common complaint among children, and studies have shown that there is a significant prevalence of back pain in school-age children (Baranda et al., 2020; Joergensen et al., 2019). The Youth Disability Questionnaire developed in Denmark emphasizes that spine pain is a multifaceted condition involving both physical and psychosocial components (Lauridsen, Meldgaard, Hestbæk, & Hansen, 2023).

The effect of carrying heavy backpacks during childhood, on the development of deformity in the spine has been a subject of curiosity. In their study, Saltikov and Cole stated that since front-use bags produce a symmetrical postural deviation in a single plane in response to the load, they would be more suitable for load carrying in the young adult student population. They stated that shoulder and handbags may cause negative stress and strain on the spinal structures by causing postural deviations in all planes and may eventually lead to pain and progressive postural scoliosis (Bettany-Saltikov & Cole, 2012).

Lack of physical activity increases the risk of poor posture by weakening the muscles supporting the spine. Lack of physical activity is also one of the most important causes of obesity in the world. Catanzariti et al. demonstrated that there was a correlation between AIS and obesity with a 2 times higher prevalence compared to the general population (Catanzariti, Rimetz, Genevieve, Renaud, & Mounet, 2023).

One of the key aspects of spine health in children is education programs. Park and Kim's study showed that a spine health education program for primary school children, which included exercises to strengthen back muscles and information about healthy foods for spine health, had positive effects on children's spine health behaviours (Park & Kim, 2011). These programs not only educate children about the importance of spinal health but also make them more attentive to spinal health (Louw et al., 2021; Park & Kim, 2011).

Furthermore, the review emphasized the need for early diagnosis and intervention in the management of spinal deformities. Regular assessment of spinal posture is crucial to detect potential problems before they progress (Lazic et al., 2021; Zmysłna et al., 2019). Integration of innovative tools such as sensorequipped backpacks can help monitor spinal development and provide real-time feedback to parents or caregivers (Yao et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, spinal health in children is a multidisciplinary issue that requires the joint efforts of parents, educators, and health care providers. The increasing prevalence of spinal disorders among children underlines the urgent need for educational initiatives that promote awareness and preventive measures. By promoting a better understanding of spinal health, we can empower children to adopt healthier habits and reduce the risk of developing spinal disorders later in life. Future research should focus on developing targeted interventions and assessment tools to further improve our understanding of spine health in the pediatric population.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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